

Novel Fibre/Resin Interface for Improved Mechanical Properties of Composites Reinforced with High Modulus Polyethylene Filaments

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ABSTRACT

The effects of plasma etching and chromic acid treatment on the surface adhesion of ultra high modulus polyethylene fibres to an epoxy resin have been studied. The adhesion was determined from pull-out tests and the results were then related to the interlammellar shear strengths and mechanisms of failure of the respective composites. The results may be summarized as follows: Both plasma and acid treatments produce a significant increase in adhesion. The mechanisms of failure, however, appear to be different in both cases. Untreated and acid treated fibres show a fairly smooth surface and failure of the system involves sliding of the fibre along the fibre/resin interface. Plasma treatment, on the other hand, produces a remarkable cellular structure on the monofilament surface, into which resin can penetrate to produce mechanical keying between fibre and resin. Failure of the system then involves rupture within the fibre.

INTRODUCTION

The discovery of ultra high modulus polyethylene (UHMPE) fibres (1) provides the possibility of producing composites which combine good mechanical properties with low specific mass. However, it is also realised that there are likely to be two aspects of the physical properties of these fibres which will make it difficult to achieve a satisfactory bond with polymer resins. First, there is the chemical inertness of linear polyethylene. Secondly, it is known that isotropic polyethylene has a low surface energy ($\approx 33 \text{ mNm}^{-1}$).

In this paper we describe improvements in the adhesion of very highly drawn polyethylene using chemical and plasma treatments. The development of wettability and interface strength was monitored by pull-out tests and exhaustive scanning electron microscopy (SEM) examination of the samples after failure. The evidence thus obtained was then related to the mechanical properties and mechanisms of failure of composites reinforced with similarly treated UHMPE yarn.

EXPERIMENTAL

Full details of the experimental procedures are given elsewhere (2,3). Here, it will suffice to say that the materials used were Unifos 2912 for

monofilaments and Sclair 2909 for yarns. Both are linear polyethylene homopolymers with $M_w = 224000$ and 102000 respectively, and $M_n = 24100$ and 17000 respectively. In all cases the fibres were melt spun at 210°C and drawn at 120°C in a glycerol bath by stretching between rollers whose relative rotational velocities were adjusted to give the appropriate draw (stretch) ratio. A low viscosity epoxy resin (Ciba-Geigy XD927) was used throughout. Chemical treatment was carried out with chromic acid, while oxygen gas was used as the plasma carrier.

Adhesion of monofilaments was measured with the pull-out technique, and the composite properties were obtained in the three point bending mode of deformation, using composite bars reinforced with continuous unidirectional yarn. The formulae for the tests (± 1 standard deviation error in brackets) are

Pull-out adhesion:	$FL/2\pi r l$ ($\pm 14\%$)
Tensile strength of monofilaments (σ_u):	$FL/\pi r^2$ ($\pm 6\%$)
Interlamellar shear strength (ILSS):	$\frac{3}{2} FL/a.b$ ($\pm 10\%$)
Ultimate flexural strength (UFS):	$\frac{3}{2} FL.c/b.a^2$ ($\pm 7\%$)
Flexural modulus (FM):	$\frac{1}{4} \delta c^3/b.a^3$ ($\pm 14\%$)

In the above expressions FL is the failure load, a (2mm) the thickness of the composite bar, b (10mm) its width and c is the span (10mm, 80mm and 160mm for ILSS, UFS and FM respectively). δ is the initial slope of the Force vs Flexural Deformation curve. All measurements were carried out at room temperature ($20.0^\circ\text{C} \pm 1.5^\circ\text{C}$).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1) Mechanical Properties

Table I shows the results of the pull-out tests and tensile strength measurements. It can be seen that both acid and plasma treatment produce significant increases in the pull-out adhesion over the very low values obtained for the untreated monofilaments. In general terms the acid treatment is most effective for intermediate draw ratio material whereas the plasma treatment is most effective for the highest (30:1) draw ratio monofilament where an improvement by a factor of about ten is obtained.

Table II gives the mechanical properties of the composites reinforced with untreated and treated UHMPE yarns (D.R. 25:1). In order to provide a standard of comparison with conventional existing materials we also tested a 2:1 glass/carbon cloth-polyester resin composite.

The ILSS measurements are normally taken as representative of the interface strength. Table II shows that the ranking of the samples agrees well with the pull-out data for D.R. 30:1 presented in Table I, although the differences obtained are not as substantial. The best ILSS value, obtained for a composite reinforced with plasma treated yarn, is only 25% lower than the ILSS of the composite taken as standard. The UFS of our composites are well below that of the standard composite, and their FM is not affected by the treatment applied to the reinforcement.

2) SEM Observations

SEM observations of pull-out samples and composites after failure have been carried out in an attempt to understand three aspects of the results presented above. a) The relationships between the observed changes in adhesion and the wettability of the fibres by the liquid resin. b) The mechanisms of failure for the different treatments and draw ratio and c) the good correlation between the adhesion in composites (as measured by ILSS) and pull-out adhesion.

2.1 Monofilaments Fig. 1 is a micrograph of the surface of an undrawn (spun) monofilament. It shows the typical dendritic surface pattern of a solidified polymer melt. Although it was not possible to perform pull-out tests on undrawn monofilaments because they are not sufficiently stiff, the interface

can still be seen by dissolving the polymer filling the groove in a fabricated test sample. The result is seen in Fig.2, which shows no evidence of the dendritic pattern and suggests that the resin does not wet undrawn, untreated monofilaments. This dendritic pattern is also retained by the undrawn monofilament after acid treatment, but this time it is well replicated by the resin after dissolving the polymer (Figs. 3 and 4). Good replication is also observed for plasma treated spun monofilaments.

Turning next to the stretched monofilaments, Fig. 5 shows the surface of an untreated monofilament of D.R. 8:1. It can be seen that the surface is smooth, except for some longitudinal striations which indicate the possible presence of fibrils (4). At a lower magnification, Fig. 6 shows that the filament surface is well replicated by the resin. It then appears that the liquid resin does not wet well undrawn, untreated monofilaments, but treatment and/or drawing improve this property to a considerable degree.

Fig. 7 shows, at an intermediate magnification, the immersed surface after pull-out of the untreated D.R. 8:1 monofilament. The surface is similar to that seen in Figs. 5 and 6, and suggests that failure involves sliding of the monofilament along the interface. The surface of an acid treated monofilament of D.R. 8:1 is seen in Fig. 8, showing that this treatment does not produce significant changes in the surface topography other than a small enhancement of the fibrillar pattern. This is well replicated by the resin but the immersed region shows the fibrillar pattern somewhat lifted-up (Fig. 9). Thus, it appears that for both the untreated and acid treated monofilaments, failure of the system involves sliding of the filaments along the interface, but in the case of the acid treated monofilaments, a significant degree of adhesion has to be overcome during pull-out. This interpretation agrees with the results presented in Table I.

All that has been said for untreated and acid treated monofilaments of D.R. 8:1 generally applies for higher draw ratios. As the draw ratio increases, the main differences are provided by an enhancement of the fibrillar pattern on the untreated monofilaments, and a significant reduction of the lifting up of the fibrillar pattern on the immersed regions of the acid treated monofilaments. For example, Fig. 10 shows the immersed region of an acid treated monofilament of D.R. 15:1. This should be compared with Figs. 6 and 8, and even more especially with Fig. 9.

The above observations agree well with the results seen in Table I, mainly with the poor adhesion associated with all untreated monofilaments, and the decreasing enhancement of the adhesion produced by acid treatment as the draw ratio increases. This last effect was to be expected as it is known that the chemical stability of the monofilaments increases with increasing draw ratio (5).

Figs. 11 and 12 show that plasma treatment produces a cellular surface on all drawn monofilaments, but the pit size increases with draw ratio, accompanied by a decrease, and even disappearance of the fibrillated surface pattern. Because the highest adhesion is obtained with plasma treated monofilaments with D.R. 30:1 we will concentrate the following discussion on this material, with the understanding that a similar discussion also applies qualitatively to plasma treated filaments with lower draw ratio.

Next we examine the immersed region of a plasma treated monofilament. In Fig. 13 it may be seen that the meniscus of the disc of resin remains on the filament after pull-out and that the immersed region is rough near the meniscus, where the pull-out force is applied. Here, we can also see evidence of fibrils failing in the tensile mode. However, Fig. 14 shows that away from the meniscus the immersed region is significantly smoother. In both cases there is no trace of the original cellular surface structure produced by the plasma treatment.

These results suggest that during the pull-out test the samples fail within the fibre, rather than at the interface between fibre and resin. It

appears that failure initiates inside the fibre, near the resin meniscus, and that the failure then propagates inside the fibre so that a skin of fibre is removed. This peel-off mechanism is confirmed by examination of the groove after pull-out. Fig. 15 shows that the groove is covered by what appears to be a layer of polymer, which we identify with the skin of the immersed fibre. Conclusive evidence for this was obtained by treating the groove with xylene at 130°C to dissolve any adhered polyethylene. The very remarkable result is shown in Fig. 16. Not only has the polymer layer apparent in Fig. 15 disappeared, but the resulting resin surface is an accurate replica of the plasma treated monofilament surface shown in Fig. 12. We conclude from these observations that pull-out samples including plasma treated monofilaments do not fail at the interface, but inside the fibre. This is likely to be associated with the high adhesion values obtained with these systems (see Table I) and it is possible that mechanical interlinking between fibre and resin plays an important role in bringing about this drastic increase in adhesion.

Fig. 17 shows at intermediate magnification the boundary between the immersed (top) and non-immersed (bottom) regions of a plasma treated monofilament with D.R. 8:1. On the immersed region there is evidence of peeling-off, but the broad details of the fibre surface goes through the boundary into both regions. Therefore, the peel-off layer is very thin, corresponding to the much finer pits on the surface produced by plasma treatment compared with higher drawn material.

From the discussion above it appears that the very high adhesion values obtained with plasma treated monofilaments with D.R. 30:1 (see Table I) may be understood, at least initially, in terms of the increase in pit size with increasing draw ratios. This allows more effective keying between resin and monofilament, and the peel-off proceeds deeper inside the monofilaments as the draw ratio increases.

2.2 Composites We will now relate the evidence and conclusions presented above for the failure mechanisms of pull-out test samples with the mechanisms operating during the failure of composites. Bars already tested for UFS were repeatedly bent by hand until the failure was complete, and we cut sections of the regions of interest for SEM examination.

Fig. 18 shows the surface of an untreated filament yarn, and Figs. 19 and 20 are the same magnification photograph of a failed composite reinforced with such a yarn. Figs. 18 and 19 show that the filament surfaces are basically similar before incorporation into composites and after the fibres have pulled out of their sockets. Fig. 20 gives evidence of the good replication achieved by the resin in contact with the filament surface. Thus, the untreated yarn filaments have slid out of their sockets along the interface, a similar failure mechanism to that seen in pull-out tests of untreated monofilaments.

Fig. 21 shows the surface of a plasma treated filament yarn with the expected highly developed cellular pattern, although the pits are about an order of magnitude smaller than those obtained with monofilaments of similar draw ratio. Figs. 22 to 25 show photographs of failed composites reinforced with plasma treated yarn. In Figs. 22 and 23 we see filaments which have pull-out of their sockets after composite failure. These show no trace of the original cellular surface structure but, instead, smooth and rough regions suggesting a peel-off failure mechanism similar to that seen in failed pull-out specimens including plasma treated monofilaments. Fig. 24 shows that the empty sockets of the failed composite are lined by what appears to be the "other side" of the original cellular surface layer on the plasma treated yarn. Dissolving this layer in hot xylene reveals the true interface (Fig. 25), showing that the resin has produced an excellent replica of the original surface of the plasma treated yarn (compare with Fig. 21). It therefore appears that the mechanisms of failure of composites reinforced with treated or untreated UHMPE yarn agree well with the mechanisms of failure discussed for

pull-out samples with similarly treated UHMPE monofilaments. These similarities explain the good correlation found between the pull-out adhesion (Table I) for monofilaments and the ILSS of composites reinforced with similarly treated yarn (see Table II).

Finally, Fig. 26 is a photograph of a failed composite where all the reinforcement (untreated yarn) have been dissolved in hot xylene. It shows the excellent penetration of the resin among the individual filaments. A similar situation applies for treated yarn.

CONCLUSIONS

- 1) Untreated UHMPE fibres show very low adhesion to resins. However, chemical treatment produces a significant increase in adhesion, and an even more substantial increase is produced by plasma treatment.
- 2) Systems containing untreated or chemically treated fibres fail at the interface, while systems containing plasma treated fibres fail inside the fibres. It is likely that interlinking between fibre and resin contributes to the high adhesion related to plasma treatment.
- 3) Pull-out tests with monofilaments provide a simple and reliable technique for studying the mechanisms of failure of composites reinforced with yarn.

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TABLE I

Pull-Out Adhesion and Tensile Strength of Monofilaments

D.R.	Treatment	Pull-Out Adhesion MPa	Final Tensile Strength GPa
8:1	None	0.6	0.30
	Acid	2.4	0.31
	Plasma	2.6	0.31
15:1	None	0.5	0.70
	Acid	2.2	0.71
	Plasma	2.7	0.64
30:1	None	0.5	0.98
	Acid	1.4	0.85
	Plasma	4.9	0.58

TABLE II

Mechanical Properties of Composites

Treatment	ILSS MPa	UFS MPa	FM GPa
Untreated	14.0	122	18.0
Acid	21.5	-	-
Plasma	28.5	122	18.0
2:1 Glass/Carbon Cloth-Polyester Resin			
	40	827	43.3

Fig.1: Untreated monofilament, D.R. 1:1, X5000.

Fig.2: "Dissolved" groove, untreated monofilament, D.R.1:1 X5000.

Fig.3: Acid treated monofilament, D.R.1:1, X5000.

Fig.4: "Dissolved" groove, acid treated monofilament, D.R. 1:1, X5000.

Fig.5: Untreated monofilament, D.R. 8:1, X5000.

Fig.6: Groove, untreated monofilament, D.R. 8:1, X300.

Fig.7: Immersion region, untreated monofilament, D.R. 8:1, X1000.

Fig.8: Acid treated monofilament, D.R. 8:1, X5000.

Fig.9: Immersion region, acid treated monofilament, D.R.8:1, X5000.

Fig.10: Immersion region, acid treated monofilament, D.R.15:1, X5000.

Fig.11: Plasma treated monofilament, D.R. 8:1, X5000.

Fig.12: Plasma treated monofilament, D.R. 30:1, X5000.

Fig.13: Immersion region near meniscus, plasma treated monofilament, D.R. 30:1, X1000.

Fig.14: Immersion region away from meniscus, plasma treated monofilament, D.R. 30:1, X5000.

Fig.15: Groove, plasma treated monofilament, D.R. 30:1, X5000.

Fig.16: "Dissolved" groove, plasma treated monofilament, D.R. 30:1, X5000.

Fig.17: Immersed/non-immersed boundary, plasma treated monofilament, D.R.8:1, X1000.

Fig.18: Untreated yarn, X5000.

Fig.19: Composite failure, untreated yarn, X2000.

Fig.20: Composite failure, sockets of untreated yarn, X2000.

Fig.21: Plasma treated yarn, X5000.

Fig.22: Composite failure, plasma treated yarn, X2000.

Fig.23: Composite failure, plasma treated yarn, X5000.

Fig.24: Composite failure, sockets of plasma treated yarn, X10000.

Fig.25: Composite failure, "dissolved" sockets of plasma treated yarn, X5000.

Fig.26: Composite failure, "dissolved" sockets of untreated yarn, X200.